

Hydro Chemical Study to Assess the Quality of Water Produced by Reverse Osmosis Plants in Residential Complexes Tobruk City

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Abstract: This study represents an assessment of the quality of drinking water produced by reverse osmosis (RO) stations within residential complexes in the study area (Tobruk-Libya), which number ten stations distributed within the city limits during the winter and summer seasons of 2022-2023. The aim was to determine their suitability for drinking based on the Libyan Specification for Drinking Water No. (82) of 1992 and the World Health Organization (WHO) standards. The results indicated that most of the physical and chemical properties were within the permissible limits, with temperature being affected by seasonal changes but remaining within acceptable values. The results also revealed significant differences between seasons, as most results were lower in winter compared to summer. Stations (7, 8, 9) in winter and stations (8, 9) in summer showed values within the permissible limits for electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, total hardness, sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium. Despite the significant decrease in total dissolved solids relative to the recommended upper limits and slight variations between stations. pH, phosphate and ammonia levels were consistently within safe drinking water limits at all stations. Microbiological analysis results showed slight contamination at stations (1, 5, 10) during the summer only. Heavy metal analysis, such as iron and manganese, showed that most stations were within safe drinking water limits, except for a slight increase in iron concentration at station (5) during the winter. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicated statistically significant differences at value ($P < 0.05$) in all studied TDS and EC parameters in winter and summer, except for temperature, phosphate and ammonia. The study concluded that the water produced from the studied RO plants in Tobruk is generally safe for drinking according to local and international standards, with some limited problems at some stations. The study recommended strengthening the RO plant infrastructure by introducing modern technologies to improve operation and purification processes to ensure water quality.

Key words: Water quality • Drinking water • Chemical properties • Reverse osmosis • Microbial characteristics

INTRODUCTION

Many Arab countries suffer from a severe scarcity of fresh drinking water, which prompts them to search for alternative sources such as desalination of seawater, wastewater treatment, and mixing saltwater with high-quality water [1]. At the same time, the demand for drinking water is increasing sharply with the increasing

population growth and economic development witnessed by most countries of the world [2]. Desalination of saltwater has emerged as a vital solution to the global water crisis, especially in Arab countries that suffer from scarcity of fresh water, such as Libya [3].

In different civilizations, the quality of drinking water significantly affects social stability, economic growth and integrated water resources management, which is crucial

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for sustainable development that addresses the challenges of water scarcity [4]. Although Libya relies mainly on water supplies from groundwater sources in southern Libya, which account for 97% of Libya's water supply, water scarcity still exists in some northern areas [5]. More than 81.3% of Libya's population lives in the coastal strip, with varying water needs, with urban areas needing 400 liters per day, while rural areas need only 150 liters [5]. Integrated water resources management is a tactical solution to combat water scarcity, which is essential for sustainable development and diverse water supply needs. However, coastal basins in Libya face significant challenges such as depletion and quality degradation due to seawater intrusion, highlighting the need for effective management strategies [6]. In light of the water crisis in the study area of Tobruk city - eastern Libya, reverse osmosis stations have recently spread in the neighborhoods within the city to provide water and fill the deficit, and the private sector has intervened by establishing drinking water stations produced using reverse osmosis technology because the current status of the main seawater desalination station in Tobruk city covers less than a third of the city's drinking water [7]. Therefore, this study aims to find out whether the reverse osmosis stations spread within the city's neighborhoods have completed their operational stages or if there are stages that have been dispensed with due to their cost. The study also aims to evaluate some of the properties of

the water produced from these stations from a physical, chemical and microbial perspective, in addition to comparing the results obtained from the produced water with the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization to determine the extent of its compliance with the appropriate specifications for drinking water (WHO).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

General Description of the Study Area: The city of Tobruk is located in northeastern Libya, bordered to the north by the Mediterranean Sea, and in terms of geographical location, it is located between longitudes 05'00"23east and latitudes 32005'00" north, as shown in Figure (1). Tobruk is also considered a coastal city with a distinct geographical and historical character, as it is 1,400 kilometers east of the capital, Tripoli. The city of Tobruk is a border area with the Arab Republic of Egypt, which increases the need for water due to expatriate workers. According to statistics and Census Authority (2022), the city's population of Tobruk reached about 202,174 thousand people. The climate of the region is characterized by being semi-desert, but it was affected by the neighboring Mediterranean climate (hot and dry in summer and warm and rainy in winter), which affected the temperatures, as the average temperature was (°31) during the summer, while in the winter (°15).

Fig. 1: The geographical location of the study area.

Fig. 2: Locations of stations in the study area

Table 1: Geographical data of station locations in the study area

No.	Longitude	Latitude	Height above sea level M	Depth M
1	23.84628 ° E	32.07968 ° N	78	88
2	23.92761 ° E	32.05851 ° N	60	72
3	23.94882 ° E	32.06182 ° N	61	70
4	23.94281 ° E	32.08581 ° N	36	44
5	23.95478 ° E	32.08271 ° N	15	18
6	23.96207 ° E	32.04028 ° N	95	109
7	23.99023 ° E	32.08255 ° N	14	16
8	23.97713 ° E	32.09332 ° N	22	27
9	23.93101 ° E	32.08558 ° N	49	61
10	23.10338 ° E	32.10338 ° N	29	34

Source: Public Water Authority - Benghazi

Sampling Program: This aspect includes several important steps starting from collecting samples during the winter and summer seasons by collecting water samples from the wells of reverse osmosis stations before and after desalination, which number 10 stations, to conduct physical, chemical and microbial analyses and three replicates for each sample before and after desalination. The sampling sites were identified using a GPS device and represented on the map as shown in Figure (2). Transferring samples to the laboratory for the purpose of conducting microbial tests in sterile bottles in less than two hours. Conducting physical and chemical tests of water samples in the study area and comparing the results of water samples in the study area with the Libyan standard specifications for drinking water No. (82) of (1992) and the specifications of the World Health Organization to determine their suitability for drinking [8].

Method of Analyses: The temperatures of the sampled waters were measured at the sites by a mercury thermometer graduated from (0-100). The pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were measured using digital conductivity meters immediately after sampling. Water samples collected in the field were analyzed in the laboratory for dissolved oxygen (DO), it was determined by the Winkler method as stated in [9] after carefully collecting water samples in 250 ml glass bottles with tight openings, without allowing air bubbles to occur during filling. The major ions (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , HCO_3^- , CO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- , NO_3^-), using the standard methods as suggested by the American Public Health Association [9]. Sodium (Na^+) and Potassium (K^+) were determined by flame photometer. Total hardness (TH) as $CaCO_3^-$, Calcium (Ca^{2+}), carbonate (CO_3^-), bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) and chloride (Cl^-) were analyzed by volumetric methods. Sulfates (SO_4^{2-}) were estimated using the colorimetric technique. Both iron (Fe) and manganese (Mn) were estimated by Atomic Absorption Spectrometers.

Microbial Analysis: The total number of bacteria was estimated using the Pouring Plate Method to estimate the microbial load using Violet Red Bile Agar, Violet Red Bile Glucose Agar and Tryptone Bile Glucuronic media. Incubation at 37-42°C was followed by shaking the sample to homogenize it and withdrawing 1 ml from the series of decimal dilutions and placing it in a Petri dish, then adding the special culture medium for growing bacteria, and moving the dish in a Circular motion counterclockwise and in a direction of the clockwise and

leaving it to solidify, then incubating in an upside down manner at a temperature of 37°C for *E. coli* for 24 hours.

Statistical Analysis: The (T. Test) was used to conduct a statistical comparison for each element between the wells in the summer and in the winter for the study areas. The One Way ANOVA test was also used for statistical comparison for each element between the two seasons at a significant difference level of less than 5%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Temperature: Temperature is one of the important properties of water, as it plays an important role in chemical reactions and dissolution of minerals. High temperatures can increase the ability of water to dissolve salts and minerals, which leads to a change in the chemical composition of the water, as high temperatures increase microbial activity, which can affect water quality [10]. According to the data in Table (2), the highest temperature was recorded in the summer at 32.3°C at Station No. (4), while the lowest temperature was recorded at 20.1°C in the winter at Station No. (5), with a general average of 24.2°C. The reason for the difference in water temperatures may be due to seasonal changes, as temperatures rise in hot seasons and decrease in cold seasons. These changes are considered natural, and although the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization (WHO) did not recommend indicative values for drinking water temperatures, it is preferable for the water to be cold rather than warm.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO): Based on the data shown in Table (2) where the highest value of dissolved oxygen was recorded at 7.5 mg L⁻¹ in the summer at Station No. (2), while the lowest value of dissolved oxygen was recorded at 6.5 mg L⁻¹ in the winter at Station No. (4), with an average of about 6.9 mg L⁻¹. The presence of dissolved oxygen in water is very necessary for the biological decomposition processes of organic materials and preventing the formation of harmful products to the environment, toxic compounds and unpleasant odors. In addition to the fact that its deficiency leads to an increase in the activity of anaerobic microorganisms [11].

pH: The results indicate that the highest and lowest values were in the winter at both stations No. (8, 3), respectively, by (6.9-6.5) and with a general average of (6.7), as shown in Table (5). All study results are within the permissible range for drinking water according to the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization, which specified that the permissible value for drinking water for pH is (6.5-8.5). PH has no direct impact on consumer health, but it is considered one of the most important indicators that determine the quality of water quality. The recommended range between 6.5 and 8.5 is considered essential to ensure the quality and health of drinking water [12].

Total Dissolved Salts (TDS): Based on the data in Table (2) it is clear that there are differences between the studied stations in the winter and summer seasons, as the highest value of total dissolved salts and the lowest value

Table 2: Physical and chemical analysis of station water in the study area during the summer and winter seasons after the desalination process

No	Depth	Height above sea level	Temperature		DO		pH		TDS *		EC *		T.H		ALK	
			M	M	C	mg L ⁻¹	-	mg L ⁻¹	μS/cm	mg L ⁻¹	mg L ⁻¹	mg L ⁻¹	mg L ⁻¹			
Unit	M	M	C	mg L ⁻¹	-	mg L ⁻¹	μS/cm	mg L ⁻¹								
			Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer
1	88	78	21.7	24.1	6.7	7.4	6.5	6.6	437 c	611 d	652 c	917 d	163	210	34.7	57.83
2	72	60	23.3	24.6	6.8	7.5	6.8	6.7	107 a	170 b	159 a	254 b	30	55	8.5	24.73
3	70	61	22.6	24.3	6.7	7	6.9	6.6	544 c	140 b	812 c	210 b	204	65	43.2	22.5
4	44	36	22.7	32.3	6.9	6.5	6.6	6.8	391 b	151 b	584 b	226 b	145	61	31.1	23.3
5	18	15	20.1	24.4	6.9	6.6	6.8	6.6	946 d	297 c	1412 d	445 c	359	109	75.2	34.23
6	109	95	23.5	27.8	6.6	6.7	6.7	6.7	684 c	751 d	1021 d	1125 d	258	287	54.4	68.27
7	16	14	21.4	30.1	7.2	7	6.8	6.8	77 a	122 a	115 a	183 a	24	38	6.1	21.1
8	27	22	20.4	26.5	7.4	6.6	6.5	6.6	48 a	87 a	72 a	130 a	20	48	3.8	18.5
9	61	49	22.2	25.5	6.7	6.7	6.6	6.6	58 a	65 a	87 a	104 a	22	24	4.6	17.1
10	34	29	22.8	24.8	7	6.9	6.7	6.7	324 b	365 c	483 b	548 c	119	153	25.7	39.37
Min			20.1	24.1	6.6	6.5	6.5	6.6	48	65	72	103	20	24	3.8	17.1
Max			23.5	32.3	7.4	7.5	6.9	6.8	946	751	1412	1125	359	287	75.2	68.27
Lib 1992													500			
WHO 1984					14.6-7.5			8.5-6.5	1000						200-170	

• Results in all columns represent the average of three replicates. The results of TDS and EC followed by the same letter within each column do not differ significantly from each other according to the least significant difference test at 5%.

were recorded in the winter season in each of Station No. (5, 8) respectively by (946, 48) mg L⁻¹, and the general average was 318.8 mg L⁻¹. By comparing the results with the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization standards, which set the permissible value for drinking water at 1000 mg L⁻¹, it is clear that each of Stations (7, 8, 9) in the winter season after the desalination process, and station (8, 9) in the summer after the desalination process did not exceed the permissible limit. The reason for the difference in the values of total dissolved salts can be explained by the difference in the desalination plants in terms of the type of devices, their degree of efficiency, filters, cells, and the quality of water used in each station in the study area. In addition, the statistical analysis of T. Test (Table 2) showed the presence of statistically significant differences between the averages of total solids for the stations in both summer and winter at a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$.

Electrical Conductivity (EC): The results showed a significant difference in electrical conductivity values as shown in Table (2), where the highest and lowest electrical conductivity values were recorded in the winter season at (1412, 72.2) micro-Siemens/cm² respectively in both stations No. (5, 8), with a general average of 476 micro-Siemens/cm². Electrical conductivity is closely related to salinity and total dissolved solids. Comparing the results with the specifications of the World Health Organization, which sets the maximum permissible concentration of dissolved salts in drinking water at 2300 micro-Siemens/cm². The results of all stations are considered suitable for drinking in both seasons. The statistical analysis T. Test proved the existence of significant statistical differences at a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$. The results also showed the existence of a correlation between electrical conductivity and physical and chemical properties. The maximum correlation was reached with TDS, where $r = 1.000$ at a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$ (Table 7). This is normal because electrical conductivity depends on the concentration of dissolved materials in water.

Total Hardness (T.H): From the data shown in Table (2), the highest and lowest values of total hardness were recorded in the winter season in both stations (5, 8) respectively by (359 and 20 mg L⁻¹), and the annual average of total hardness was 119.8 mg L⁻¹. When comparing the results with the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization, which

set the permissible limit for the total hardness rate in drinking water as 500 mg L⁻¹, it becomes clear that all stations in both seasons fall within the permissible limits for drinking purposes, and this is consistent with the study.

Alkalinity: Alkalinity is a measure of the ability of water to modify the acidity caused by the presence of carbonate, bicarbonate and hydroxide ions. Based on the data recorded in Table (2), differences in alkalinity rates are noted, as the highest and lowest alkalinity values were recorded in the winter at both stations No. (5, 8) respectively by (75.2, 3.8) mg L⁻¹, and the annual average for alkalinity was 30.7 mg L⁻¹. The World Health Organization (WHO) set the guide value between 170-200 mg L⁻¹, and through the results reported, all results were within the permissible limits for drinking.

Sodium (Na⁺): The results shown in Table (3) indicate that the highest value recorded was in the summer at Station No. (6) at 138.0 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value was recorded in the winter at Station No. (8) at 8.0 mg L⁻¹, and the general average was 44.3 mg L⁻¹. Measuring sodium concentration is considered one of the most important factors used to determine the quality and suitability of water [13]. By comparing the results with the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization standards, which specified that the permissible range for drinking water is 200 mg L⁻¹, we find that all stations fall within the permissible limits for drinking water according to the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization.

Potassium (K⁺): The data in Table (3) show that the highest value was recorded during the winter at Station No. (6) at 11.5 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value was recorded in the summer at Station No (9) at 0.90 mg L⁻¹, with a general average of 5.3 mg L⁻¹. Potassium is the seventh element in terms of its presence in natural water, as its concentration is low in most drinking water, and may reach only 20 mg L⁻¹, while it reaches more than 100 mg L⁻¹ in sea water. When comparing the results with the specifications of the World Health Organization, which set the permissible concentration of potassium for drinking water at 20 mg L⁻¹, and comparing the results with the Libyan standard specifications, which set the permissible range for drinking water at 40 mg L⁻¹, it appears that all station water falls within the permissible limits for drinking water.

Table 3: Physical and chemical analysis of station water in the study area during the summer and winter seasons after the desalination process

No	Depth	Heigh above sea level		Na (mg L ⁻¹)		K (mg L ⁻¹)		Ca (mg L ⁻¹)		Mg (mg L ⁻¹)		NH ₄ (mg L ⁻¹)	
		M	M	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer
1	88	78	55	78	9	6.9	48	65	15	15.4	0	0.05	
2	72	60	27	23	2	3.1	8	17.9	2.1	5.7	0.1	0.01	
3	70	61	80	19	12	1.8	55	14	17	6.9	0	0.04	
4	44	36	46.8	22.8	3.1	1.9	48	12.7	10.18	7.1	0.1	0.01	
5	18	15	96	48.7	25.1	3.4	126	31.2	18.8	8.1	0.1	0.02	
6	109	95	85	138	11.5	7.4	76	71.1	12	18	0	0.06	
7	16	14	12	18.9	2.8	1.8	7.9	13.8	1.2	3.2	0.1	0.01	
8	27	22	8	14.7	3	1.1	6.9	9	0.5	2.1	0	0.01	
9	61	49	9	11	1.2	0.9	6.99	7.4	0.8	1.8	0	0.01	
10	34	29	43	51	3	4.8	33	41	8	13.1	0.1	0.03	
Min			8	11	1.2	0.9	6.9	7.4	12	1.8	0.12	0.01	
Max			96	138	25.1	7.4	126	71.1	190	18	0.67	0.06	
Lib 1992			200		40		200		150		0.5		
WHO 1984			200		20		200		50		1.5		

• Results in all columns represent the average of three replicates.

Calcium (Ca⁺⁺): The results in Table (3) showed that the highest and lowest values of calcium were recorded in the winter season at both stations No (5, 9) respectively, reaching (126, 6.9 mg L⁻¹), with a general average of 34.9 mg L⁻¹. Calcium is one of the main elements that make up water hardness and affects the use of water for domestic purposes. When comparing the results with the specifications of the World Health Organization and the Libyan standard specifications, which set the permissible concentration for drinking water at 200 mg L⁻¹, we find that all station waters were within the permissible range for drinking water.

Magnesium (Mg⁺⁺): The results recorded in Table (3) show that the highest and lowest values in magnesium concentration during the winter season in both stations No. (5, 8) respectively amounted to (18.8, 0.5 mg L⁻¹), with a general average of 8.3 mg L⁻¹. Magnesium ion is one of the most common alkaline elements in water and is characterized by its high ability to dissolve in water, as it is similar to calcium ion, and water in which magnesium concentration exceeds 125 mg L⁻¹ is not suitable for drinking, and has an effect on human health, especially on the intestines [12]. When comparing the results with the specifications of the World Health Organization, which set the permissible limit for drinking water at 50 mg L⁻¹, and comparing the results with the Libyan standard specifications for drinking water, which set 150 mg L⁻¹, all stations during the two study seasons fall within the permissible limits for drinking water.

Ammonia (NH₄): Ammonia plays an important role in assessing the quality of drinking water, as high

concentrations indicate the presence of contamination that may affect public health, which requires careful monitoring in water treatment systems. The results recorded in Table (3) show that the highest value of ammonia was recorded in the winter at each of stations No. (2, 4, 5, 7, 10) by 0.10 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value of ammonia was recorded in the winter at each of stations No. (1, 3, 6, 8, 9) by 0.0 mg L⁻¹, and the general average of ammonia is 0.04 mg L⁻¹.

When comparing the results with the Libyan standard specifications, which set the permissible range for ammonia concentration in drinking water at 0.5 mg L⁻¹, and with the World Health Organization specifications for drinking water, which set 1.5 mg L⁻¹, it becomes clear that all Water stations falls within the permissible range.

Sulfates (SO₄⁻): From the results recorded in Table (4), the highest value of sulfates was recorded in the winter at Station No (5) at a rate of 226.0 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value was in the summer at Station No (9) at a rate of 13.0 mg L⁻¹, and the average for the year was 70.8 mg L⁻¹. When comparing the results according to the specifications of the World Health Organization and the Libyan standard specifications that set the permissible value for drinking water as 400 mg L⁻¹, it appears that all station waters comply with the specifications of the World Health Organization and the Libyan standard specifications for drinking water.

Chloride (Cl⁻): The results recorded in Table (4) indicate that the highest concentration of chloride was recorded in the summer at Station No. (6) at a rate of 230.0 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value was in the winter at Station No. (8)

Table 4: Results of sulfate, chloride, phosphate, nitrate and bicarbonate values for stations in winter and summer after desalination

No	Depth	Height above sea level		SO ₄ (mg L ⁻¹)		Cl (mg L ⁻¹)		PO ₄ (mg L ⁻¹)		NO ₃ (mg L ⁻¹)		HCO ₃ (mg L ⁻¹)	
		M	M	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer
1	88	78		108	116	85	177	0.001	0.03	10	3.9	105	65
2	72	60		31	41	28	51	0	0.07	3	0.7	30	15.3
3	70	61		132	37.4	110	49	0.001	0.06	14	0.6	145	13.3
4	44	36		85	39.1	81	50	0.002	0.08	15	0.7	79.1	14.8
5	18	15		226	58.1	198	105	0	0.06	14	1.3	156	19.77
6	109	95		107	125	189	230	0.002	0.01	13	4.1	63.6	98
7	16	14		21	29.7	15	39.6	0	0.06	2	0.5	20	10.9
8	27	22		35	15	9	31	0	0.04	0.04	0.4	7	7
9	61	49		37	13	11	19	0	0.03	0.1	0.3	2.1	15
10	34	29		81	79	71	131	0.004	0.063	15	2.1	37	21.4
Min				21	13	9	19	0	0.01	0.04	0.3	2.1	7
Max				226	125	198	230	0.004	0.08	15	4.1	156	98
Lib 1992				400		250		—		45		—	
WHO 1984				400		250		0.4		45		200	

• Results in all columns represent the average of three replicates.

at a rate of 9.0 mg L⁻¹, with a general average of 83.9 mg L⁻¹. Chloride is one of the important negative ions found in natural water and gives water a salty taste, especially if it is associated with sodium ions. When comparing the results with the specifications of the World Health Organization and the Libyan standard specifications, which set the permissible value of chloride for drinking water at 250 mg L⁻¹, we find that all station water is within the specifications of the World Health Organization and the Libyan standard specifications for drinking water.

Phosphate (PO₄): The results, as shown in Tables (4), show that the highest value of phosphate concentration was in the summer at Station No (4) where it reached 0.08 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value was recorded in the winter at Stations No. (2, 5, 7, 8) and reached 0.000 mg L⁻¹, and the average for the year was 0.03 mg L⁻¹. Although the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization did not specify a guideline value for the concentration of phosphate in drinking water, the guidelines issued by the European Community Group of States in 1992 recommended that the permissible limit for phosphate concentration in drinking water is 0.4 mg L⁻¹. Accordingly, all stations fall within the permissible limits for drinking water.

Nitrates (NO₃): They are chemical compounds that contain nitrate ions, and are considered common pollutants in drinking water. Nitrates can arise from several sources, such as agricultural fertilizers, sewage, and industrial pollution [16]. Through the results recorded

in Table (4), it was found that the highest value of nitrates during the winter season was in both Station No (10) at a rate of 15.0 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value was recorded in Station No (8) during the winter season as well at a rate of 0.04 mg L⁻¹, and the average general concentration was about 5.0 mg L⁻¹. When compared with the specifications of the World Health Organization, which set the permissible range for nitrate concentration in drinking water at 45 mg L⁻¹, we find that all station water is within the permissible limits for drinking water. Research study by Abdalmula *et al.* [13] stated that the increase in nitrate concentration in drinking water causes suffocation in infants due to the effect of nitrates on the blood's inability to transport oxygen, and the presence of nitrates greatly affects the deterioration of water quality.

Bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻): The results shown in Table (4) that the highest and lowest concentration of bicarbonate during the winter season in both stations No. (5, 9) respectively at a rate of (156.0, 2.10 mg L⁻¹), and a general average of 46.3 mg L⁻¹. When compared with the specifications of the World Health Organization, which set the permissible value for drinking water at 200 mg L⁻¹, we find that all station water is within the permissible limits for drinking water. The presence of carbonates and bicarbonates in water affects the degree of hardness. Study by Omran and Zayed [14] indicate that increasing the concentration of bicarbonate in drinking water helps stabilize the pH and improve the flavor, while its deficiency leads to increased acidity, which may cause pipe corrosion and water contamination with heavy metals.

Table 5: Results of iron and manganese values for stations in winter and summer after desalination

No	Depth	Height above sea level	Fe (mg L ⁻¹)		Mn (mg L ⁻¹)	
			Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer
Unit	M	M				
1	88	78	0.04	0.02	0.09	0.02
2	72	60	0.06	0.01	0.06	0.01
3	70	61	0.07	0.01	0.03	0.01
4	44	36	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
5	18	15	0.18	0.02	0.03	0.02
6	109	95	0.11	0.04	0.01	0.04
7	16	14	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01
8	27	22	0.03	0	0	0
9	61	49	0.03	0	0	0
10	34	29	0.01	0.02	0.07	0.02
Min			0.01	0	0	0
Max			0.18	0.04	0.09	0.04
Lib 1992			0.3		0.1	
WHO 1984			0.3		0.1	

• Results in all columns represent the average of three replicates.

Table 6: Results of microbial analyses of stations in winter and summer after desalination

No	Depth	Height above sea level	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	
			Winter	Summer
Unit	M	M		
1	88	78	- Ve	+Ve
2	72	60	- Ve	- Ve
3	70	61	- Ve	- Ve
4	44	36	- Ve	- Ve
5	18	15	- Ve	+Ve
6	109	95	- Ve	- Ve
7	16	14	- Ve	- Ve
8	27	22	- Ve	- Ve
9	61	49	- Ve	- Ve
10	34	29	+Ve	+Ve

• Results in all columns represent the average of three replicates.

Bold samples are positive

Iron (Fe): The results in Table (5) show that the highest value recorded for iron concentration during the winter at Station No. (5) by 0.18 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value was recorded during the summer at Station No. (8, 9) by 0.00 mg L⁻¹, and the average for the year is 0.04 mg L⁻¹. After comparison with the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization, which set the permissible range for iron concentration in drinking water at 0.3 mg L⁻¹. In this study results indicate that all station water falls within the specifications of the World Health Organization and the Libyan standard specifications for drinking water. Rosen and Rainey [15] stated in their study that the presence of iron in high concentrations can cause an unpleasant metallic taste in the water, which reduces human acceptance of consuming this water.

Manganese (Mn): The results recorded in Table (5) show that the highest value of manganese during the winter season was at station No. (1) by 0.09 mg L⁻¹, while the lowest value of manganese concentration was recorded during the winter and summer seasons at stations (8, 9) by 0.00 mg L⁻¹, and the general average was 0.02 mg L⁻¹. After comparison with the Libyan standard specifications and the World Health Organization specifications that set the permissible range for manganese in drinking water at 0.1 mg L⁻¹, it becomes clear that all station water is within the specifications of the World Health Organization and the Libyan standard specifications for drinking water.

Microbial Analysis: The data in Table (6) indicate the presence of microbial pollution, as the data recorded the presence of pollution during the summer at stations No. (1, 5, 10), while pollution appears in the winter only at station No. (10). Microbial contamination of drinking water is one of the most dangerous sources of the spread of epidemics and diseases such as typhoid, cholera, viral hepatitis and diarrhea. The presence of a group of coliform bacteria in water is a general indicator of pollution, which can be primarily from nature or from human or animal feces and includes *Escherichia Coli* bacteria. The contamination of water produced from stations with *E. coli* bacteria may be attributed to several factors, including the presence of black wells (traditional sewers) near groundwater wells, which date back decades. Also, the reason may be due to the direct discharge of sewage from some residential buildings, where it is injected into groundwater wells or cavities under the ground surface, which leads to the pollution of waterways and the flow of pollutants towards groundwater wells.

Correlative Studies among Physical and Chemical Components of Drinking Water: The results also showed the existence of a strong positive correlation between temperature and physical and chemical properties of drinking water such as temperature (r=0.705), EC (r=1), TDS (r=1), Na where (r=0.705), HCO₃ (r=0.772), NO₃ (r=0.772) at a significance level of P≤0.05. However, some components showed the absence of a correlation between them and the physical and chemical properties like pH and ammonia. It is evident that there were inter correlative studies among the chemical component of drinking water where the maximum correlation was reached with EC where r = 0.996 and Na where r = 0.941 and calcium and physical and chemical properties. The maximum relationship was with Na, where r = 0.874 at a significance level of P≤0.05. Results, indicating that the increase in

Table 7: The relationship between physical and chemical properties in summer and winter season.

Correlations																			
	T	DO	PH	TDS	EC	caco3	alkalinity	Na	K	Ca	Mg	NH4	So4	Cl	po4	No3	Hco3	Fe	Mn
T	1																		
DO	-0.326	1																	
PH	0.241	-0.121	1																
TDS	-0.199	-0.125	0.205	1															
EC	-0.197	-0.125	0.203	1.000 ^{**}	1														
caco3	-0.189	-0.163	0.194	.996 ^{**}	.996 ^{**}	1													
alkalinity	-0.005	-0.134	0.186	.965 ^{**}	.966 ^{**}	.966 ^{**}	1												
Na	-0.058	-0.192	0.217	.944 ^{**}	.944 ^{**}	.941 ^{**}	.931 ^{**}	1											
K	-0.389	-0.078	0.301	.863 ^{**}	.862 ^{**}	.864 ^{**}	.784 ^{**}	.705 ^{**}	1										
Ca	-0.271	-0.093	0.190	.983 ^{**}	.983 ^{**}	.981 ^{**}	.937 ^{**}	.874 ^{**}	.916 ^{**}	1									
Mg	-0.097	-0.145	0.180	.928 ^{**}	.928 ^{**}	.930 ^{**}	.925 ^{**}	.904 ^{**}	.756 ^{**}	.885 ^{**}	1								
NH4	-0.294	0.206	0.281	0.240	0.239	0.223	0.153	0.204	0.179	0.270	0.134	1							
So4	-0.334	-0.069	0.221	.955 ^{**}	.954 ^{**}	.952 ^{**}	.886 ^{**}	.847 ^{**}	.930 ^{**}	.971 ^{**}	.903 ^{**}	0.268	1						
Cl	-0.025	-0.133	0.157	.951 ^{**}	.951 ^{**}	.951 ^{**}	.972 ^{**}	.957 ^{**}	.713 ^{**}	.902 ^{**}	.894 ^{**}	0.168	.837 ^{**}	1					
po4	.705 ^{**}	0.022	0.033	-0.317	-0.316	-0.300	-0.086	-0.288	-0.376	-0.328	-0.146	-0.363	-0.376	-0.136	1				
No3	-0.425	-0.156	0.216	.679 ^{**}	.677 ^{**}	.671 ^{**}	.526 [*]	.558 [*]	.635 ^{**}	.692 ^{**}	.626 ^{**}	0.375	.722 ^{**}	.489 [*]	-.572 ^{**}	1			
Hco3	-0.336	-0.162	0.284	.859 ^{**}	.858 ^{**}	.852 ^{**}	.764 ^{**}	.794 ^{**}	.858 ^{**}	.855 ^{**}	.853 ^{**}	0.243	.910 ^{**}	.691 ^{**}	-.499 [*]	.772 ^{**}	1		
Fe	-.461 [*]	-0.119	0.402	.684 ^{**}	.682 ^{**}	.683 ^{**}	.556 [*]	.535 [*]	.899 ^{**}	.750 ^{**}	.485 [*]	0.261	.745 ^{**}	.535 [*]	-.503 [*]	.532 [*]	.682 ^{**}	1	
Mn	-0.293	-0.043	0.146	0.255	0.253	0.234	0.138	0.290	0.227	0.210	0.326	.444 [*]	0.303	0.157	-0.420	0.428	0.404	0.211	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

total hardness is associated with an increase in electrical conductivity and sodium concentration. Moreover, the relation of Cl with SO₄ was evident r = 0.837 and EC where r = 0.951 and the the maximum relationship of K reached with Na where r = 0.705. The correlation between magnesium and physical and chemical properties, was with Ca, where r = 0.885 while iron relationship was reached with Ca, where r = 0.899 at a significance level of P ≤ 0.05.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that all values obtained from the results of desalination plant water were mostly within the permissible limits according to the Libyan standard specifications as well as the World Health Organization (WHO). In addition the slight contamination of the water produced from some reverse osmosis plants with E. coli

bacteria may be due the direct discharge of sewage from some residential buildings that are injected into groundwater wells. Therefore, the study emphasizes the need for periodic follow-up by the competent authorities in the state for all desalination plants in the study area to monitor the quality of water and the amount of potable production. The researcher also recommends in this study the need to implement the legal legislation issued by the state to preserve the environment in order to prevent such negative phenomena that have become a threat to drinking water produced from reverse osmosis plants in the study area.

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